

A Co-Simulation Framework of Autonomous Mobility in Urban mixed traffic Context

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Abstract—In this paper a co-simulation architecture for autonomous mobility in mixed traffic environment is proposed with the objective of providing a digital twin of the urban 3D context and estimating the shortest travel time path. In particular, different tools are interconnected to realize such co-simulation framework. SUMO is adopted to set the simulation in a large area of Bari, including a large number of intersections, traffic lights and pedestrian zones in 2D. TraCI API interface is used to manage the running road traffic simulation, retrieving values of simulated objects and manipulating their behavior in real-time. In addition, Unity is adopted to generate and manage the equivalent 3D map of the road network. In the proposed framework, the objective is to simulate the traffic including an autonomous vehicle and estimating the travel speed of such vehicle in different route alternatives, to find the minimum cost path. The proposed co-simulation architecture is demonstrated in a use case in the city of Bari considering different instances in order to evaluate the impact of the variations in vehicles number and typology on the AV speed evaluation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing number of vehicles on the road has brought great benefits in terms of mobility, but has also introduced problems such as traffic, pollution and accidents. A solution to these problems is represented from self-driving vehicles. An autonomous vehicle (AV) is defined as a vehicle capable of following a path without or with limited human intervention. In theory, this type of vehicle can be immune to human error, therefore it would be safer and more efficient than a traditional vehicle.

There is the need to solve a series of related problems to the training of these vehicles, since they must know how to correctly respect the driving rules, interact with traditional vehicles, guarantee human and environment safety and, at the same time, drive the best route based on current road conditions. The expression "best route" leads to various interpretations: given a starting point and an arrival point, the best path is not necessarily the one with the shortest distance between the two assigned points, but it could be the one with the least traffic, which allows you to arrive at your destination in less time than the one in which it is present a higher speed limit or that allows the minimum consumption fuel. It is therefore essential to use simulators in order to

recreate the real environment within which safely test and evaluate the different path solutions.

In this paper, a co-simulation architecture is proposed to create a digital twin (DT) of an autonomous vehicle traveling in a urban mixed-traffic environment. The DT is implemented using the following softwares that must be integrated:

- SUMO: traffic simulator used to create and manage road 2D networks. It allows you to include motor vehicles, to control their behavior and to acquire information on the state of the simulation.
- Unity: Graphics engine used for the creation of three-dimensional environments. It is used for viewing the 3D road network scenario and the motor vehicles in motion.

In addition, Python which is today one of the most used programming languages thanks to the simplicity of its syntax and the wide range of available libraries, it is used for interconnection of the two aforementioned environments. Therefore, the contribution of this work can be summarized as follows:

- Create a 2D traffic road network using SUMO for autonomous mobility integration in urban traffic. In particular, the road network of the city of Bari is considered;
- Create the equivalent 3D road network using Unity simulator;
- Implement the route optimization algorithm;
- Carry out simulations with autonomous vehicle in mixed traffic.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II provides a background on the related works, Section III presents the methodology to develop the digital twin of road traffic network and Section IV describes the algorithm for the route planning. Section V presents the simulation test results and the conclusions are provided in Section VI.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORKS

A. Algorithms for Autonomous mobility

The main advantage that comes from the use of self-driving vehicles is the possibility of delegating every aspect concerning driving to the vehicle, including route planning and optimization. There are several algorithms for route planning in the literature. Understanding which one to employ requires taking into consideration a series of parameters. According to the work [1], there are three items that describe goodness of a route planning algorithm: 1) computational complexity: defines how long the algorithm

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takes to converge, that is, it manages to find the optimal path. It is the metric mainly held into consideration when comparing different algorithms; 2) scalability: describes the performance degradation of an algorithm as the number of entries increases, in this context, as the road network grows; 3) quality of the solution: compare the different optimal paths found on the basis of pre-established metrics (arrival times, distance traveled, etc.) to define which is the best solution.

According to [2], the route planning problem can be divided into two main categories: the Global Path Planning and the Local Path Planning, also known as Strategic Route Planning and Tactical Route Planning, respectively [3]. The first category is based on the use of geographical maps aimed at generating an initial path in which there is no risk of collision between vehicles. When the vehicle starts the path, it is necessary to perform real-time adaptations based on the conditions of the surrounding environment (traffic, speed restrictions, etc.). This last case refers to local path planning. Most of route planning algorithms are based on graphs, A graph is a structure composed of n number of nodes (the road intersections) and an m number of connections or arcs (the road segments). An undirect graph is a graph in which the arcs are bidirectional and it well represents the network of bidirectional road segments connecting road intersections.

Authors in [1] classify the different algorithms by differentiating them between optimal, heuristic and hybrids ones. This classification can be integrated with the one proposed from the study [2]. Among the main algorithms adopted there is the Dijkstra algorithm aiming at finding the shortest path between a node x and every other node within the network. It is among the most used for finding minimum path within a graph, although it has limitations due to its $O(n^2)$ computational complexity which does not make it particularly suitable for large networks. There are some variations of this algorithm, which aim to reduce the number of paths to analyze by implementing operations pruning so as to reduce the convergence time [4]. The study [2] for example uses Dijkstra algorithm but drastically reduces the surface area of the map to analyze by taking a small area overarching the optimal path from origin to destination.

Another algorithm is the A* that as the goal of finding the best path in a graph and it is based on the minimization of the function $f(n) = g(n) + h(n)$, where $g(n)$ is the cost to reach node n , while $h(n)$ is a heuristic function that allows you to reduce the number of searches to be performed. As described in the research [8], route planning algorithms and graph-based strategies tend to have very long convergence times, such as to not make them applicable in real-time environments. To solve this problem, the study proposes a variant of A* called SAS (Sparse A* Search) which allows to limit the nodes on which to carry out the search so as to have the algorithm to converge faster and consent to use it in real-time dynamics.

Genetic algorithm is a technique that is inspired to the Darwinian concept of species selection, as described in [1], [4]. It starts from different initial solutions (the different species), or different paths, and by recombining them it

leads to new solutions (new species obtained from random genetic mutations), or other pathways. The evaluation of these solutions leads to the convergence of the algorithm (selection) and therefore to obtain the best path (only the species who adapt best survive).

Ant Colony is an algorithm which resumes what normally happens in nature in ant colonies [1], [4]. Once the path from the colony to the food source has been found, the ants release pheromones along the way to attract others ants follow the same instructions. The best path is given by fact that more ants pass over the same path again, increasing the amount of pheromone left on the ground. Based on this concept, whenever the vehicle crosses a new node, information about its position and the time taken to reach it are stored.

In addition, reinforcement learning is used in this context which consists of a technique for applying the machine learning where the system agents, in this case the vehicles, undertake actions aimed at achieving an objective [6]. These are not made explicit but are deduced by the agent himself through a complex system of rewards or punishments based on a high number of iterations. As described in the article [6], this type of approach is preferable compared to Dijkstra or A* algorithms in all cases where the environment is highly dynamic. Particularly, the method proposed in [6] is able to consider factors such as traffic lights and react to congestion by switching to the second optimal route found.

In the field of self-driving vehicles it is also essential to evaluate the routing time, i.e. the total time required by the vehicle to execute all its functions. The research [4] summarizes the four factors that influence this parameter:

- preprocessing time: time necessary to calculate the path;
- queuing time: due to the presence of other vehicles employing the requested resource;
- transmission time: time it takes the vehicle to arrive at destination;
- postprocessing time: due to waiting for the vehicle once it arrives at your destination before you can finish the process.

The extremely variable conditions of the road network make it complicated the identification of the optimal route. There are several factors that contribute to it such as the different characteristics of the vehicles, the weather conditions and different driving styles. Generally, when we talk about the optimal path we refer to the one with the lowest travel time. Therefore, the problem of speed prediction is of great importance. The article [9] provides a comprehensive study, as it describes the methodologies currently used for speed prediction, explaining what are the factors that influence the system and indicating which metrics are used when evaluating the solution. A first classification concerns the level of detail, or resolution, on which to base the model. The methods described are therefore divided into macroscopic methods, microscopic methods and mesoscopic methods an hybrid version of the first two methods.

In addition, the speed prediction methods can be differentiated in Model-based methods, Data-driven methods and Deep-learning methods [9]. The Model-based methods

are based on the use of mathematical formulas to estimate the speed of the same vehicle, while, others are based on the speed of the following vehicle. These are not suitable methods for estimation over long distances, as the data used do not provide high model accuracy. The Data-driven methods are based on statistics and/or machine learning. Based on a dataset, a model is trained that can estimate the next state of the vehicle. These are efficient methods and can guarantee good performance even in real-time. Deep-learning methods are based on the use of deep neural network and they represent the most modern approaches to such problem solving. A large amount of data can be considered in order to find patterns. In general, these methods can also model very complex systems. The main disadvantage is the high computational power required and the cost for maintaining the data. However, despite this disadvantage, usually this approach has the highest performance.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this work, we focus on the control of self-driving vehicles, especially on finding the best path given a starting position and an ending position, i.e the path with shortest travel time. In order to analyze and control the behavior of the AV, one must first make use of a simulator or DT to reconstruct the environment and test the control algorithms. The work has been carried out according to the following steps:

1. Acquisition of the road network using an open-source map.
2. Creation of the 2D environment in Sumo.
3. Sumo-Python integration via TraCI API interface.
4. Acquisition of the 3D map in CityEngine.
5. Creation of the complete 3D environment in Unity.
6. Unity-Python connection via TCP socket.
7. Python as a middleware between the two systems.
8. Implementation of the control algorithm in Python.
9. Simulations with different traffic scenarios and data acquisition.
10. Interpretation of the results.

A. SUMO environment

SUMO (Simulation of Urban MObility) is a traffic simulator released in 2001 and written mainly in Java, C++ and Python. It allows to manage very large road networks, control traffic lights, pedestrians, and perform simulations and detailed analysis of automobile traffic. Thanks to the exposed API, it is possible to interface the simulator with other systems. In this work, the TraCI API (Traffic Connection Interface) is adopted, which allows the connection and management of the simulator through a Python environment.

In this paper, SUMO is used to set the simulation in a large area of Bari, including a large number of intersections, traffic lights and pedestrian zones, as shown in Fig. 1. The data related to the road network were acquired through OpenStreetMap (OSM), an open-source tool created for the purpose of acquiring geographic data from around the world through the contributions of individual users. Sumo uses

XML files that define the roads and intersections for network generation. Once the necessary files have been created, they need to be retrieved in an XML file, which will be the one used by SUMO. The basic configuration contains only information about the duration of the simulation and reference to the network roads and the vehicles created. You can test the newly created simulation by manually opening it in SUMO, or by taking advantage of the TraCI API interface through one of the supported programming languages, such as Python. By giving access to a running road traffic simulation, TraCI allows to retrieve values of simulated objects and manipulate their behavior in real-time.

Fig. 1. Map of Bari from OSM.

B. UNITY environment

Unity is one of the most widely used graphics engines for the development of video games and real-time 3D animation [11]. One of its strengths is its broad compatibility with different hardware and software systems, which enables the development of cross-platform projects. Compared to other engines such as Unreal or Godot, Unity turns out to have a more intuitive, greater hardware compatibility, and the ability to write C# code makes it initially more easy to use, although it lacks in terms of memory used, longer rendering times and non excellent photo-realism. Thanks to the "Unity Scripting API," it is possible to impart commands to the different objects in the scene, in order to control and modify their properties. The use of scripts allows Unity to communicate with SUMO and acquire all information related to the simulation.

CityEngine is the software used for 3D modeling of immersive urban environments. It natively supports data acquisition from external software including OSM. Once the OSM file has been acquired, it is possible to specify the structures to be imported such as roads, railroad tracks, buildings, crosswalks and other road elements. The software automatically proceeds to creation of the road network and buildings, to which you can assign textures. CityEngine is

based on the mechanism of Procedural Modelling. Through the definition of the ground rule to which the model must adhere, this can be generated automatically and later refined manually or through the modification of certain parameters, such as floor plan, dimensions and colors. The final file can be saved in one of the 3D files formats supported by Unity: the model of Bari was exported as an .obj file.

The 3D model of Bari map and of the car are imported into Unity. The car object will be automatically instantiated based on the number of cars in the simulation.

The scene created in Unity is actually static, i.e., it contains a set of three-dimensional elements without any behavior. It is possible to assign actions to the scene components through C# scripts. The use of scripts is essential to: i) implement the TCP socket that will be used by Python to send real-time data to the scene; ii) synchronize the position of the vehicles based on the simulation in SUMO; iii) manage camera positioning to provide a more immersive visual experience.

C. SUMO-Unity integration

Once the static environment has been realized in Unity, Python is able to connect to the TCP socket and to update the positions of the vehicles in the scene. The following elements are present in the scene:

- Car: it represents the 3D model of the car;
- Camera: it is a virtual camera that will follow the self-driving vehicle during the simulation;
- Scripts: used to implement the TCP socket and exchange data with Python;
- Map of Bari: it represents the 3D model of Bari made with CityEngine.

Once the two environments have been made separately, the last step to be performed is the connection between the two for scenario synchronization. In this sense, as shown in Fig 2, Python acts as a middleware between SUMO and Unity. More in detail, it continuously collects the locations of the vehicles in SUMO through the methods exposed by the TraCI API interface and then sends these locations, in terms of 2D coordinates, to the scene by a TCP socket exposed by Unity.

More specifically, data acquisition at each time step goes through the following instructions: i) execution of a step in SUMO simulation; ii) acquisition of of the current location of the vehicles and their identifiers; iii) synchronization of the position in Unity. Simulation result is shown in Fig. 3.

Finally, Python is also in charge to run the control algorithm that determines the route to assign to the self-driving vehicle in SUMO by invoking specific methods exposed by the TraCI API interface.

IV. AV ROUTE PLANNING

Optimizing the path between two points does not necessarily mean finding the shortest one, but the one that goes to minimize one or more parameters. They are taken into account several factors, some of which depend on the

Fig. 2. Co-Simulation architecture.

Fig. 3. SUMO (right map) and Unity (left map) map integration.

conformation of the road network (distances and intersections), others on the dynamics of vehicles that can lead to queuing, accidents and detours. This section describes the steps followed for the implementation of the control algorithm devised to find the path at minimum cost.

A. Preliminaries

As described in the article [6], drivers tend to prefer the route that takes less time, as opposed to the one that actually covers a shorter distance. Therefore, minimization of travel time is considered. The preliminary steps to be followed for the correct identification of the best route are as follows:

- 1 Choosing a starting node and a destination node within the OSM map. It is necessary to specify starting and ending position so that alternative paths can be defined.
- 2 Identification of alternative routes. It is useful to select alternative routes to allow the algorithm to understand, based on the boundary conditions, which among them turns out to be the best. The control algorithm will calculate the travel time for each path and will assign to the vehicle the shortest time route.

3 Inclusion of routes within the SUMO configuration previously created. Once selected, the paths are saved in a .rou.xml file containing the list of nodes traversed by each path, along with an identifier of the path itself. The path identifiers are used in Python to acquire and analyze the routes, and assign the best one to the AV.

B. Estimation of travel times

The estimation of travel time is based on the model proposed by the study [12]. The illustrated model ties the speed of the individual vehicle to the concept of traffic density. In the traffic model there are vehicles of different categories, sizes and performance: smaller vehicles (such as motorcycles) will tend to flow faster than larger ones (such as buses or trucks). The study proposes a math model for estimating the speed of each vehicle category within a certain flow (in this case, the route is divided into edges, or sections, each one with a travel speed). Knowing the length of the individual road section, once the speed of the vehicle is calculated, it is possible to derive the travel time of the AV for each section. The total travel time is given by the sum of the travel times for all the segments.

This same calculation is repeated for all vehicle categories present in the network. In this work the selected vehicle classes or categories in SUMO are three: 1) Passenger car; 2) Bus; 3) Motorcycle.

We use the following equation to compute the vehicle velocity per vehicle class:

$$V_i = a_0 - \frac{a_1 n_1}{V_1} - \frac{a_2 n_2}{V_2} - \frac{a_3 n_3}{V_3} \quad (1)$$

where V_i represents the speed of the vehicle of category $i = 1, 2, 3$; a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3 are the regression coefficients; n_1, n_2, n_3 represent the number of vehicle of class 1, 2 and 3, respectively; V_1, V_2, V_3 indicate the vehicle speed of a specific category. All necessary data to compute equation (1) can be retrieved through the TraCI API interface and the Sumolib library that allow to analyze the OSM map imported in SUMO.

The following procedure is defined in order to find the shortest time path for the considered AV of class 1:

- 1 Acquire the alternative paths.
- 2 For each path, acquire the segments and features.
- 3 Acquire the length of the individual edge and the number of vehicles present for each category.
- 4 Use equation (1) to calculate the estimated speed for the considered AV in each segment.
- 5 Save the travel time for the AV in class 1 for each trip segment.
- 6 Estimate the total travel time for the AV.
- 7 Repeat the steps 4-6 for all alternative paths.
- 8 Return the route with shortest travel time and assign it to the AV.

Afterwards, the estimated travel time can be compared with the actual travel time, so that the error can be evaluated.

V. SIMULATION TESTS

This section reports the results of simulations carried out in order to test the validity of the algorithm and its accuracy according to certain parameters. The simulations have been conducted on a 12th Gen Intel Core i7 CPU, 3600Mhz, RAM 16GB. In particular, the accuracy was evaluated in two scenarios: 1) varying number of vehicles; 2) varying typology of vehicles in the urban traffic simulation scenario.

This first simulation aims to evaluate the accuracy of the model implemented as the number of vehicles changes. This turns out to be a key parameter since the the AV speed in the individual trip segment is based on the number of vehicles present for each category. It is evaluated in two subcases: 1a) 100% of vehicles are of category 1; 1b) 60% of vehicles of category 1, 20% of vehicles of category 2, 20% of vehicles of category 3. The results are shown in Fig. 6: the blue profile represents case 1a) results while the orange profile represents case 1b) results. Note how the presence of heterogeneous vehicles (case 1b) causes a larger error in estimating the AV travel time then in case 1a. As can be seen, the accuracy of the model presents an almost constant error and tends to decrease for a number of vehicles equal to 600. Over 600 vehicles the error begins to increase. It can be due to the following reasons: When number of vehicles is relatively low, some terms of equation (1) can be null and the presence of the known terms a_0 lead to have a constant error; the growth in the number of vehicles necessarily leads to the congestion in the road network.

Fig. 4. Travel time estimation error over total vehicle number.

In the second simulation scenario, the traffic road network is simulated varying the number of total vehicles, i.e. 600 or 1000, according to the best results found in the first scenario. In addition, in order to evaluate the impact of the start time of the traffic, the case with 600 vehicles is repeated two times. Therefore, three cases are considered: 2a) 600 vehicle, start time 60sec.; 2b) 600 vehicle, start time 180sec.; 2c) 1000 vehicles, start time 180sec.

Each of the three above cases is repeated in 10 different instances, by varying the vehicle composition per category, to evaluate the impact on the speed evaluation error.

Fig. 5 shows the speed evaluation error on travel time varying the vehicles composition per category in cases 2a,

2b, 2c. Varying the traffic composition will vary its density and consequently the calculated travel time.

From Fig. 5 the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The highest errors pertain to the simulation conducted on 1000 vehicles, due to the static nature of the implemented algorithm that ignores the dynamic evolution of the system.
- Simulations containing a high percentage of passenger cars cause the largest errors.
- Under mixed traffic conditions the error tends to be constant.
- The algorithm estimates the time with greater accuracy in cases in which motorcycle traffic is higher because it represents the class of vehicles with the highest dynamism and least influence on travel time.

Fig. 5. Travel time estimation error comparison on several instances of mixed-traffic.

Fig. 6. Intersection crossing simulation with SUMO and Unity.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a digital twin of mixed traffic scenario including an autonomous vehicle is proposed based on a co-simulation architecture. The presented co-simulation architecture is realized integrating two main software, i.e. SUMO

and Unity. SUMO is adopted as traffic simulator of 2D road networks. It allows to include motor vehicles, to control their driving behaviors and to retrieve information on the state of the simulation. Unity is a graphic engine adopted for the creation of three-dimensional environments. It is used for the visualization of the 3D road network scenario and the motor vehicles in motion. Moreover, Python is adopted for the interaction of SUMO and Unity.

The objective of the co-simulation architecture is to find the minimum travel time cost path for the autonomous vehicle in the considered urban traffic scenario from departure to destination. A simulation campaign demonstrates the application of the integrated traffic model in the city of Bari.

Future works will enlarge the number of autonomous vehicles considered in the mixed traffic urban scenario in order to simulate a fleet of autonomous vehicles.

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